

Reimagining Intranet Platforms for Higher User Engagement

Namratha Peddisetty

nammscool4u@gmail.com

Abstract

Intranet platforms play a vital role in enhancing collaboration and communication, apart from just acting as a tool of information sharing. But the issue a lot of companies' face is how to increase user engagement within the platform. This article explores different strategies of how organizations can improve user engagement on their Intranet platform. This article also presents a few live cases about how organizations leveraged their intranet solutions. These case studies will provide examples of how intranet can be used not only to solve internal communication needs, but also can contribute to the creation of a strong connected culture.

Keywords: Employee Engagement, Intranet Design, Content Management, Digital Workplace

INTRODUCTION

An intranet is a computer network for sharing information, easier communication, collaboration tools, operational systems, and other computing services within an organization, usually to the exclusion of access by outsiders[1]. Intranet solutions have been used in organizations for a long time as an internal only communication, document exchange and collaboration tool. Until recently, these platforms were built for efficiency with a focus placed purely on how employees could use them to access important materials and information about what was going on within the company. However, the traditional intranet standalone platforms are no longer adequate in today's dynamic environment. Especially with the changing nature of work, where work has largely become digital with a lot of tools, and with remote work surge, employees can all be collaborating from different parts of the country or world, the intranet platform should be seen as an important and powerful tool for collaboration. User engagement on intranet platforms has a lot of benefits. All the engagement will increase a sense of belonging among the employees and in turn help increase productivity and decrease attrition rates. But, if the platform is hard to navigate and is not rich in functional features the employees require, they will not be as eager to access it. However, if the platform layout is good and is also engaging for the users, it would become a part of employees' daily activity stream — and make communication and working on projects much more effective. Intranet platform also serves as a tool to reinforce brand and company's culture [2]

Evolution journey of Intranet platforms [3]

STRATEGIES TO INCREASE USER ENGAGEMENT

To increase employee engagement with the intranet, businesses should implement a range of activities that reflect the employees' needs and wants. Below are a few strategies that can be incorporated for increasing user engagement on intranet platforms

User-Centric Design:

User-centric design is designing by keeping the user at the center. Gather feedback, collect insights on customer needs before designing the platform. Keep the design simple and easy to navigate. User-friendly interfaces with layout and navigation that provide the ability on demand to organize all information that has to do with the employees, their work, and specific projects further extend the usage of the platform and engagement.

Mobile first:

In the current day, where everything is available at the fingertips of the users via their mobile, having an intranet app available on their mobiles would help them connect and collaborate from anywhere, even on the go. This will in turn increase the engagement of users because of easy availability.

Content Management:

Sharing of content is the main way of how an Intranet platform gets used. Hence it is very important on the type of content that is being shared. Companies must strategize and create an editorial calendar that has details like what, when, who. It is not just the future content that the companies need to think around, but also the past content needs to be maintained and archived so that the information can stay relevant and up to date. Employees also need to be encouraged to generate their own content. It also fosters ownership since the employees are encouraged to contribute material to the organization.

Auto Landing Intranet page

Companies can default the users to land on an Intranet homepage where they can view the latest news and updates and start their day with a sense of belonging.

Beyond content sharing

Intranet platforms are no longer viewed as a platform only for sharing content [4]. The role of the intranet as a personalized gateway to a diverse internal application landscape is thus becoming increasingly important. In its function as a digital gateway, the intranet can either link to specific tools in the digital workplace or offer so-called “microservices” from these tools directly on the intranet. [2]

Sense of being heard

Employees should not feel as though the functionalities or design is being forced upon them. There needs to be a feedback mechanism through which employees can share their feedback online or reach out to the intranet team for any issues.

Minimize number of channels for communication purposes

With the increasing choices of tools, it is very important for a company to avoid using multiple channels for communication and craft a strategy on which tools will be used when and use the intranet platform for posting most of the information.

Leveraging Modern Technology

Leverage AI / Generative AI or robust search technologies that can help the users find the information they are looking for very easily and in turn make the usability easy for the users.

Case studies of how some companies increased user engagement on their Intranet Platforms

AI on MetLife’s Intranet: [4]

MetLife Intranet Leveraged Future work AI Chatbot to provide employees guidance and resources on topics such as COVID-19 and MetLife’s hybrid-working model. It was one of the most used resources on their intranet in three years [3]

Virtual assistant on Infosys’s Intranet:[4]

The InfyMe chatbot, that could answer questions on hardware and software support and business processes of Infosys was used by 305,867 unique users and has handled 919,075 questions with an average accuracy of 88% in 2 years.[3]

Fostering collaboration at AbbVie

AbbVie designed its intranet with an aim to connect its employees to news, information, people and systems and created communities for knowledge sharing and ideas fostering collaboration, connection and authentic employee engagement [3].

Employee retention at ServiceNow

ServiceNow developed a manager Hub on the intranet, which served as a single source for career development and access learning resources all at one place. [3]

Conclusion

Intranet platform serves as a great collaboration tool which when employed correctly can create a sense of belonging and help boost user productivity. Some of the crucial tactics that enhance users' engagement on the intranet platform are to include user-centered design, mobile optimization, and appropriate content management tactics. Organizations that invest in this area shall clearly benefit through enhanced communication and collaboration as well as enhanced staff satisfaction. Since organizational work environment is ever dynamic, intranet platforms will require constant evolution incorporating users' feedback to enhance their efficiency.

References

- [1] "Intranet." Wikipedia.com. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intranet>
- [2] F.Wolf. "The Ultimate Guide to Modern Intranet: Boost Your Digital Employee Experience." Staffbase.com. <https://staffbase.com/blog/modern-intranet/>
- [3] A.Kaley, M.Rosala, K.Pernice, and P.Caya "The 10 Best Intranets of 2023: Trends in Design and Process." Nngroup.com. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/intranet-trends/>